

PHARMACEUTICAL PROPERTIES OF CALENDULA OFFICINALIS

Mamatkulov Z.U.

Tashkent Pharmaceuticals Institute, medicine of means industry technology
department associate professor

Kayumova G.G.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Biotechnology department assistant,
kildonferuz@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8405011>

Calendula officinalis (Calendula), Asteraceae to his family, usually known as English Marigold or Pot Marigold fragrant grass is traditional _ medicine in the system for ulcers, stomach ulcers, herpes, scars, skin injury, cold and the cold in treatment is used blood cleaning. Its different biological activities because of analgesic, diabetes, wound and inflammation against diseases treatment is used. It is also gastrointestinal, gynaecological, and eye diseases of skin damage and some burns in cases used. Calendula fat is still medicinal _ to the tumour against tools and wound healer tools as is used. Plant pharmacological studies that's it showed that calendula extracts are antiviral, anti- genotoxic in vitro properties In plant science suspension or in tincture calendula acne in treatment, inflammation different appearances in reduction, blood to leave control in doing and scratching feature giver tissues calm down for is used. Calendula from the plague protection to do for is used. Ancient medicine calendula gangrene treatment was _ First from help besides, calendula food digestion to do tool is also used as Infusion form of flowers or Tincture, various infections and diarrhoea in treatment is useful. Calendula officinalis infusion, as well as a bee the sting of the eye inflammation, varicose veins, eczema, mouth space washing or tooth the pain relief for use can _ This is blood and lymph of fluids rotation improves and from the organism toxins out to send help gives _ This is a plant carotenoid, flavonoids, glycosides, steroids and sterols quinines, volatile fats and amino acids such as many chemical active rich in substances. of this plant extract and from him separated pure compound cytotoxic, hepatoprotective and spasmolytic such as many pharmacological to activity have the fact that years during studied bride _ People Calendula officinalis in medicine to inflammation against, diaphoretic, pain leaving, antiseptic and yellow in treatment used _ However, the plant flowers therapeutic in terms of the most strong the fact that note done _ This meritocratic of the plant pleiotropic features wound against HIV _ against, immunity instigator, injury healer effect shows. inside is mucus of floor inflammation, stomach and ten two-fingered intestine ulcers, gastrointestinal tract spasms, ten two-fingered intestine and intestine mucus

floor, and dysmenorrhea for is used. (painful menstruation) especially nervous or anaemia with sick in women, spleen and liver inflammation. Usually, external use in cases of skin inflammation, open wounds and blood leaving with torn wounds treatment for clinical as is given From this except, a razor burn and the wind burn such as small diseases treatment for is used. From this except for, the tooth from getting after mouth washing

Использованная литература:

1. Jolene H. Eat prity.2014. Nutrition for beauty, inside and out. China:
2. Edition 1 .
3. 2- Geneva, 2005; Available from: [http// www.who. Int/ iris / handle /](http://www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/69229)
4. 10665 / 69229.
5. 3- Bucca B. pino A. Almonti A. Forte G. 2014. Toxic metals report Requ.
6. Toxicol pharmacology. 68 (3): 447 – 67.
7. 4- Ibrahim S. Abbas . 2013. Effect of biological competition of weeds on
8. Growth and volatile Oil yield of marigold (*Calendula officinalis* L.) As
9. medicinal plant used in herbal medicine of Iraq. Int.J. of pharm. And
10. pharmaceutical Research. 6(1). 217 – 219.
11. 5- Bashir S, Giliani AH ,2008. Studies on the antioxidant and analgesic
12. activities of Aztec marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) flowers. phyther Res. 22:
13. 1692 -1694 . doi: 10.1002 / ptr .2550 .[pubMed] [cross Ref] .g tool as is used.